

DISTRIBUTION OF TWO IONS BETWEEN ION EXCHANGER AND SOLUTION

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How the distribution of two exchangeable ions between an ion exchanger and the external solution depends upon the concentration ratio of the two ions in the solution, at some constant total concentration, has been shown. A relation, $(A/B)_R = a [(A/B)_S]^n$ gives the distribution, $(A/B)_R$ being the ratio of equivalents of two ions in the resin, $(A/B)_S$, the ratio concentrations in the solution, and 'a' and 'n', constants for a particular pair of ions in case of a particular ion-exchange resin. This is applicable both to cation exchange as well as anion exchange.

When an ion exchanger containing a particular exchangeable ion, A, is allowed to come to equilibrium with a solution of another ion, B, the two ions are distributed between the exchanger and the solution. This distribution may be characterised by what is known as the selectivity coefficient, the quotient of the ratios of the equivalents of the two ions in the exchanger and in the solution :

$$K_A^B = (B/A)_R / (B/A)_S.$$

If this selectivity coefficient, K_A^B , comes out to be equal to 1, the exchanger has no preference for either of the ions, A or B. If the exchanger be selective for B, $K_A^B > 1$ and if selective for A, $K_A^B < 1$. Uptil now there is no completely satisfactory theory, which can fully explain why in a given case an exchanger shows preference for one ion to another. This distribution of ions is dependent on various factors, e.g., nature of the exchanger, nature of the exchangeable ions, total concentration as well as concentration ratio of the exchangeable ions, temperature, etc. (Deuel and Hutschneker, *Chimica*, 1955, 9, 49).

Moqkerjee and Mukherjee (*J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1954, 2, 29) have shown that a relation $(B/A)_S = \theta [(B/A)_R]^\alpha$, where θ and α are constants, applies well to the experimental data in the case of some clays. When both θ and α are unity, the clay has no preference for either of the ions B or A; but the deviation of any system from this ideal value measures the antagonistic influence of one ion on the other. In their work, the concentration ratio was varied, but the total concentration was not kept constant. Here the study is extended to ion-exchange resins, both cationic as well as anionic; further, the total concentration of the ions in the solution has been always kept at a constant value.

The object of the present paper is to show how the distribution of ions depends on the concentration ratio for some typical ordinary ions, keeping the variable, total concentration, at some constant value. For the ion exchangers, both cationic and anionic ion-exchange synthetic resins have been used.

EXPERIMENTAL

'Zeokarb 225' and "De-acidite FF" were used as cation and anion exchangers respectively.

"Zeokarb 225" is a mono-functional strong acid cation exchanger based on cross-linked polystyrene containing the sulphonic acid group as the ionogenic group. The particles are spherical in shape between -16 and +50 mesh size. The moist Na-form of the resin as obtained was thoroughly regenerated with about 4N-HCl. The regenerated resin in its H-form was then thoroughly

washed with distilled water until free from chloride and acid, and then dried in air at the room temperature. From this regenerated H-form of the resin its Na-form and Ca-form were prepared by replacing the H^+ ions completely with $NaCl$ and $CaCl_2$ solutions respectively.

"De-Acidite FF" is also a mono-functional strong base anion exchanger, available in bead form between -16 and $+50$ mesh size. The original moist Cl-form of the resin was first completely converted into its OH-form by 3% NaOH solution and then thoroughly washed with distilled water. The Cl-form, which was used for the experiment, was prepared from this regenerated resin with the help of $N-HCl$.

In all the cases the resins after being thoroughly washed with distilled water and then dried in air at the room temperature were kept in well-stoppered bottles.

Procedure.—Weighed quantities of the air-dried resins (~ 1 g.) were taken in columns and were leached, in case of the cation exchanger, with mixtures of chloride solutions of two cations other than the one present in the resin, and in case of the anion exchanger, with mixtures of potassium salt solutions of two anions other than the ion saturating the resins. Three different concentration ratios ($0.2N$ and $0.1N$, $0.15N$ and $0.15N$, $0.1N$ and $0.2N$) were used for the leaching, keeping the total concentration of the solutions constant at $0.3N$. The leaching was continued till complete displacement of the ion originally present in the resin. The free electrolytes were then washed away from the resin with distilled water. In case of the cation exchangers, the two adsorbed cations were completely leached out with an excess of $N-HCl$, and estimated in the leachate. In case of the anion exchangers, the two adsorbed anions were leached out with $N-NaOH$ solution and were analysed in the leachate.

Potassium was estimated gravimetrically by weighing as perchlorate. Ammonium was estimated by distilling its salt solution with NaOH, absorbing the liberated ammonia in excess of a standard H_2SO_4 solution and then titrating the unchanged acid by a standard alkali solution. Calcium was precipitated as oxalate, and after ignition of the oxalate, it was weighed as CaO . Barium was estimated volumetrically by the chromate method, and magnesium gravimetrically as pyrophosphate. Bromide was estimated by titrating the solution, made slightly acidic with HNO_3 , with a standard $AgNO_3$ solution using iodoeosin as indicator. Nitrate was reduced to NH_3 and then estimated after distilling it off. Sulphate was calculated as the difference between the total amount of anion present in the resin and that of the associated nitrate ions. The reproducibility of the analytical results was found to be within $\pm 2\%$.

The results for the cation exchanger in its H-form, Na-form and Ca-form are presented in Table I where 'C' represents the ratio of the concentrations of the ions A and B in the solution used for the leaching, $(A/B)_S$, and 'm', the ratio of equivalents of the ions A and B adsorbed in the resin, $(A/B)_R$.

DISCUSSION

It is observed from Table I that in no case the ions are adsorbed in the same proportion as these are present in the leaching solution. Further, the distribution of the two ions does not depend on the form of the resin. This is, of course, to be expected as finally the ion originally saturating the resin has been completely replaced by the two ions. In the $K^+-NH_4^+$ mixture the exchange of K^+ is increased or that of NH_4^+ is decreased, and the extent of interaction is almost the same at all the three concentration ratios as is evident from the almost constant value (1.2) for $(K^+/NH_4^+)_R / (K^+/NH_4^+)_S$. From the mixture $Ca^{2+}-NH_4^+$, Ca^{2+} ion highly suppresses the

Log m , when plotted against log C (vide Table I), gives straight lines with different slopes and different intercepts on the log m -axis for different pairs of ions. A typical plot is shown in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1

H-Zeo-karb 225.

 $K^+ / NH_4^+ - C$, $Ba^{2+} / Ca^{2+} - A$ and $Ca^{2+} / NH_4^+ - B$.

FIG. 2

R-OH and R-Cl.

 $NO_3^- / Br^- - B$ and $NO_3^- / SO_4^{2-} - A$

The relationship between 'm' and 'C' can be mathematically expressed in the form, $m = aC^n$, where a and n are constants. The values of a and n for a particular pair of cations, as determined from the graphs, are shown in Table II for the three forms of the resin.

TABLE II

System.	a .	n .
H-Resin : K^+ / NH_4^+	1.2	1.0
Ca^{2+} / NH_4^+	4.3	0.7
Ba^{2+} / Ca^{2+}	3.5	0.9
Na-Resin : K^+ / NH_4^+	1.2	1.0
Ca^{2+} / NH_4^+	4.0	0.7
Ba^{2+} / Ca^{2+}	3.7	0.9
Ca-Resin : K^+ / NH_4^+	1.2	1.0
Ba^{2+} / NH_4^+	9.5	0.7
Ba^{2+} / Mg^{2+}	9.1	0.6

The deviation in values of a and n from unity shows that one ion suppresses or enhances the adsorption of the other ion, i.e., the resin is selective towards one of the ions. The more the deviation, larger will be the selectivity.

The behaviour of Mg^{2+} in presence of Ba^{2+} is found to be more akin to the monovalent NH_4^+ rather than to the bivalent Ca^{2+} .

It is observed from the results presented in Table II that irrespective of the form of the resin, a particular pair of competing ions has almost the same values of a and n . The average values of a and n for a particular pair of ions are summarised in Table III.

TABLE III

Pair of ions.	a .	n .
K^+/NH_4^+	1.2	1.0
Ca^{2+}/NH_4^+	4.2	0.7
Ba^{2+}/Ca^{2+}	3.6	0.9
Ba^{2+}/NH_4^+	9.5	0.7
Ba^{2+}/Mg^{2+}	9.1	0.6

The results for the anion-exchanger resin in its OH-form and Cl-form are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Anion mixtures.	OH-Resin.					Cl-Resin.				
	C.	m .	m/C .	$\log C$.	$\log m$.	C.	m .	m/C .	$\log C$.	$\log m$.
NO_3^- (A) } Br^- (B) }	2.0	2.0	1.0	0.30	0.30	2.0	2.0	1.0	0.30	0.30
	1.0	1.1	1.1	0.00	0.04	1.0	1.1	1.1	0.00	0.04
	0.5	0.56	1.1	-0.30	-0.25	0.5	0.54	1.1	-0.30	-0.27
NO_3^- (A) } SO_4^{2-} (B) }	2.0	5.7	2.9	0.30	0.76	2.0	5.9	3.0	0.30	0.77
	1.0	3.3	3.3	0.00	0.52	1.0	3.3	3.3	0.00	0.52
	0.5	1.6	3.2	-0.30	-0.20	0.5	1.6	3.2	-0.30	0.20

Table IV shows that both for OH-form and Cl-form of the resin, NO_3^- and Br^- enter the resin almost in the same ratios as these are present in the leaching solution. Considering the slightly higher value than unity of m/C , it may be said that NO_3^- has slightly suppressed the entry of Br^- . But the system $NO_3^- - SO_4^{2-}$ presents a peculiar behaviour. Though SO_4^{2-} is known to have a higher replacing power than NO_3^- , its adsorption is lowered in presence of the latter. The ratio of the sulphate to nitrate adsorbed in the resin is about one third of the corresponding ratio in the solution.

It is observed that $\log C$ and $\log m$ have same values for a particular pair of anions in both the hydroxyl and chloride forms of the resin, and so have been plotted in the same Fig. 2. Here also the plots fall almost on straight lines, just as in the case of cation-exchange processes and the ratio of the amounts of the two anions (which completely replace a third anion saturating the resin) in the resin phase is related to their ratio of concentrations in the leaching solution according to the same equation :

$$(A/B)_R = a [(A/B)_S]^n.$$

The characteristic values of the constants a and n for the two different pairs are given below.

TABLE V

Pair of anions.	a .	n .
$\text{NO}_3^- / \text{Br}^-$	1.1	0.9
$\text{NO}_3^- / \text{SO}_4^{2-}$	3.1	0.9

From the above results it may be concluded that the distribution of two ions depends on their concentration ratio according to the relation,

$$(A/B)_R = a [(A/B)_S]^n,$$

the values of the two constants a and n being characteristic for a given pair of ions in case of a particular ion exchanger.

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